

Total Physical Response and Direct Method: Impact on English Speaking: Vocabulary Improvement.

Mr. Pradip Kumar Mahata

Faculty of English at Garhbeta College

Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal

Research Scholar at C V Raman Global University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

Corresponding Author

Prof. Dr. Pragyan Paramita Pattnaik

Professor and Head

Department of Humanities and Social Science

C V Raman Global University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

Abstract

The primary goal of this investigation was to show how the Total Physical Response (TPR) method and Direct Method increase English vocabulary to improve English speaking skills. For fluent English speaking, an enriched vocabulary is required. Vocabulary development is one of the most important things to do to develop uninterrupted speaking ability. TPR is the language learning method that encourages children to acquire their mother tongue and is also used to teach other languages. This study used qualitative and quantitative methods for conducting the research. After analysing the scores of English vocabulary, the data were evaluated using descriptive statistics using IBM SPSS 25. Sixty students will be selected as sample through the random sampling method in an equal proportion from secondary and higher secondary from Jhargram district's. For the study, three groups were formed: a "control group", "TRP experimental group." and a "DM experimental group." The data collection tool for this research was a vocabulary evaluation with MCQs and matching questions. Each group was given a preliminary test of the technique before it was implemented. In the meantime, a post-treatment test was performed to test the improvement. Post-tests were given to all three groups after they had received the prescribed teaching using each method. The t-test revealed the existence of a significant difference. During the research it has been found that Total Physical Response outperformed Direct Method in vocabulary teaching in English to students in secondary and upper secondary schools. The control group improved by 2.20 points, the TRP experimental group improved by 11.35 points, and the DM experimental group improved by 5.70 points.

Keywords: Total Physical Response, Direct method, Vocabulary and Speaking Skills.

Introduction

In today's world, English has become one of the most important subjects to learn. Therefore, English teaching should begin at an early age (at the school level). James Asher developed the total physical response. Language and action are synchronised in this approach. Students carry out the teacher's instructions. Maximilian Berlitz developed Direct Method in France and Germany around 1900. It is often also called as the 'phonetic method,' 'Anti grammatical method,' 'natural method', and 'reform method'. This method was a reaction against the GTM method. My research is going to analyse how effectively the Total Physical Response and Direct Methods to

enrich the individual's vocabulary for spontaneous English speaking skills. The span of time during which a person picks up additional languages or vocabularies in their brain is referred to as language acquisition. (Iskandarwassid & Sunendar, 2009). Acquisition of a language takes place at a young age or when a person gets their first language, also referred to as their mother tongue. (Hashim & Yunus, 2018). Unlike studying a language, language learning is a natural process. It is an automatic and unplanned process. On the other hand, when we talk of learning a new language, we're talking about the processes that take place when a new language is presented. Teaching a new language to a child through the natural method through conversation in the target language is more effective. According to Crain (2014), one of The Piagetian stages of child development occurs within the range of ages 2-7, and throughout this time, children have a greater

need for concrete situations to process ideas than they do for abstract ones.

Consequently, it is recommended that youngsters be taught language in a context-based manner. It is recommended that language should teach to youngsters in a specific context. 15-16-year-olds are inquisitive. It needs growth-promoting activities. Students in elementary school who are learning English have various challenges, particularly with pronouncing and comprehending the meaning of words. Thus, vocabulary plays an essential part in the English speaking skills, especially for secondary students. This age is prominent for Language development. They should be educated not just in their own tongue, but also in other languages. A child's first step in learning a foreign language is acquiring a functional vocabulary. It implies that young students should expand their vocabulary before moving to other linguistic building blocks like grammar and composition. Children's memory and cognitive growth will benefit greatly from early exposure to a second language. (Faqihatuddinitah, 2016).

When teaching vocabulary, the researchers, in this case, adopted the TPR as contrary to the DM. With the direct method, students acquire new words directly from their English teachers from real-world objects, large amounts of oral engagement, and spontaneous language usage; there is no function of translation needed between the first and second languages. (Brown, 2001: 21). Total Physical Response, however, is an approach to education that uses physical activity, visuals, and tangibles to help students learn new words in English. (Brown, 2001: 29). It's a practical method of imparting an exact definition of each English vocabulary word to students, and it may also aid in their ability to retain the meanings of those words later on. Therefore, either the TPR or DM method of teaching English vocabulary is effective and may be used. Furthermore, the instructor has not covered any of those strategies in Bengali and other vernacular medium schools. It's a practical method of imparting an exact definition of each English vocabulary word to aid in students' ability to retain the meanings of those words later on. Therefore, either the TPR or DM teaching methods of teaching English vocabulary are effective and may be in use. Furthermore, the instructor has not covered those strategies in Bengali and other vernacular medium schools. Writers chose this theme for numerous reasons. Indian students struggle with English learning. Second, they thought TPR or DM might be a fun way to learn vocabulary. TPR or DM fit young learners' learning styles. Third, TPR or DM was supposed to make primary and secondary school students like English more. Fourth, the instructors have not extensively taught Total Physical Response and Direct Method in their classes.

Review of Literature

The primary reason why communication activities should include in the class is that all humans need to communicate to convey their ideas, emotions, and opinions. The students are involved in a stimulating learning environment that motivates them to complete their assignments, and they speak more efficiently. All individuals comprehend spoken language as per their contexts, including everyday life, community, school, work, and others. Actively practicing a language in class is excellent. Instead of explaining grammatical principles, teachers should encourage spontaneous speech of the foreign language in class. Students might then understand grammatical rules. Mime presentation and visuals may be utilised to teach new vocabulary via the usage of familiar terms. Franke (1884) According to Titone (1968), the instructions that follow might be considered as an illustration of the principles: Never give a speech; instead, perform; never explain; instead, demonstrate and query. Always communicate in complete sentences instead of just words to avoid misunderstanding. A teacher who uses elaborate metaphors and wordplay to explain Japanese vocabulary when a simple translation would have done the trick

more effectively. To be sure, there have been other approaches to teaching a foreign language, but the Direct Method is the first to garner widespread interest among educators and experts in the field. In many ways, it was the start of the Methods Age. Roger Brown (1973:5) to put it simply, TPR is an approach to teaching languages that emphasises the connection between words and deeds. 'Total Physical Response' (TPR) might observe as a strategy of teaching in which students mimic their instructor's actions after hearing a remark from the instructor. In Total Physical Response (TPR), students of all skill levels learn to respond actively in the classroom instruction process. According to Richards and Rodgers (2001: 87), presentation and action may convey a foreign language's meaning without translation or the learners' native language. The direct approach had a well-defined structure by the turn of the century when the phrase "Direct Method" was coined to describe it. Eventually, the Direct Method advanced in many ways beyond international borders. There has been a notable increase in the progress rate of students learning a fresh vocabulary because of the innovations introduced by the Direct Method. Richards and Rodgers (2001: 11) Students' Difficulty Communicating in Class is a Major Issue in English Classes. The fundamental principles provided in this article are intended to provide a foundation for further study of the communicative method and linguistic theories that might be applied in an English Language classroom. To help their pupils develop their speaking skills, instructors should look for appropriate communicative activities in print and digital media. It is the responsibility of educators to provide difficult assignments that push their pupils to the limits of their abilities. Speaking clarity is a significant skill for students to improve in authentic contexts using the linguistic forms and patterns they have learned. Sepevsiova [2015]. If pupils use English regularly helps with their speaking, despite the stress it may cause. Therefore, it is essential to propose efficient means of adapting either the TRP or DM English teaching method for a better result in English speaking skills.

Objectives, Research Questions and Hypothesis

English speaking skills difficulty is a common problem for Bengali and other vernacular medium schools. To reduce this common nightmare for students, this research is going to find the following issues:

- To observe the impact of TRP and DM in ESL English classes.
- To see the impact of newly improved vocabulary in fluent speaking skills.
- To observe that the aforesaid methods make the class interactive or not.

The researcher hypothesised that there is a major impact of TRP and DM in occupying new vocabulary that helps the learner to adopt fluent English speaking ability much better than earlier methods of teaching.

Method

A research endeavour requires a research plan to conduct more impartial and accurate research results. This study used both qualitative and quantitative methods. In this research, Vocabulary development for speaking ability is the dependent variable, whereas Total Physical Response and Direct Methods are the independent variables. For this research, the population consisted of sixty students from Jhargram district's secondary and higher secondary schools throughout the school year 2022–2023. The sample will be selected through the random sampling method in an equal proportion from both streams of schools. For the study, three groups were formed: a "control group" and two "experimental groups." One control group for TPR and another 'control group' for DM. The research tool was a vocabulary evaluation with MCQs and matching questions. Each group was given a preliminary test of the technique before it was implemented. In the meantime, a post-treatment test was performed to test the improvement. Post-tests were given to both experimental groups after they had received the prescribed teaching using each method. After analysing the scores of English vocabulary, the data were evaluated using descriptive statistics. The t-test revealed the existence of a significant difference.

Data Collection:

Research participants were students in the 10th grade during the 2022–2023 school years. Researchers used a four-part procedure to carry out the study: evaluating the approach, having participants experience the treatment, and collecting data thereafter. The authors collected the data, When the pupils finished the exam, a score was assigned.

Data Analysis:

After accumulating the data, the authors performed the necessary analysis. The authors processed the test results once the scoring was complete. There were 20 questions in the exam. Each question was awarded one mark if answered correctly and zero points if answered incorrectly during scoring. After getting individual score will be calculated in percentage. The authors used these procedures to gather and evaluate the necessary data for the study:

- The authors gathered data. The pretest-posttest ratio was calculated.
- The authors statistically analysed the test scores to determine homogeneity and normalcy. The authors used one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for multivariate normality and independent sample test for homogeneity.
- Using the t-test formula for independent samples, the authors examined the hypothesis after obtaining the results.

The authors tested the null hypothesis, normality, and homogeneity using IBM SPSS 25 for Windows 10, the formula for a t-test as an example.

Validity Test:

These authors employed content and construct validity in their research. In the absence of any suitable statistical tools, the issue of content validity was left to the discretion of the experts. The researchers consulted about the questions included in the test. The authors employed the Pearson Product Moment Formula to determine the reliability of the constructs. The authors gave a trial run to students at another institution before administering the pre-test at the students' primary institution. The purpose of the trial run was to determine the test's validity and reliability. There were a total of 10 questions on the examination.

Data is valid if the Pearson correlation test r-value exceeds the r-table result. Check the r-table for statistical significance at 5% ($p=0.05$).

Table - 1

Correlation

Tota l	Pearson Correlatio n	.718* *	.718* *	.729* *	.597* *	.620* *	.538* *	.580* *	.514* *	.597* *	.718* *
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.000									
	N	60									

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

- N= Number of respondent,
- 'DF' = N-2,
- 'Obtained Value' >'Critical Value' in the table.
- Our 'Number of respondent' is 60 =N.
- $DF=N-2=60-2=58$ DF in the table.
- $58 DF (.05)=0.2542$

Now we can see that every single one of the Pearson correlation values (.7180, .7180, .7290, .5970, .6200, .5380, .5800, .5140, and .7180) is larger than 'Critical Value' of 0.2542. So, the author observes that the validity of the questionnaire is valid.

Reliability Test

The researchers then used the Cronbach Alpha formula in IBM SPSS 25 for Windows 10 PRO to determine the test's reliability once they had established its validity. The dependability of the examination was determined to be 0.818. As

Ghozali claims (2011: 42), "If Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.60, we may conclude that the instrument is credible". Since 0.831 was more than 0.60, we may infer that the instrument was dependable. Take a look at the graph below to see the impact of reliability

Table - 1

The Reliability Test Result.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.831	10

Pre-test Analysis

On November 7, 2022, a preliminary examination was held for members of both the experimental and control groups. Forty pupils took part in the exercise. There were two groups of twenty students each. One was experimental and other served as a control group. The goal of this exercise was to assess

the pupils' English vocabulary knowledge before administering any treatment. There were a total of 20 questions on the vocabulary exam, 12 of which were multiple-choice with four possible answers and 8 of which were matching. Both the control and experiment groups were given a preliminary test, the results of which are included in Appendices - II

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		CGPRTMRK S	TRPPRETM ARKS	DMPRETMA RKS
N		20	20	20
Normal Parameters^{a,b}	Mean	56.5000	57.3500	56.0000
	Std. Deviation	3.62012	3.57292	2.79096
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.161	.145	.113
	Positive	.161	.145	.113
	Negative	-.107	-.128	-.076
Test Statistic		.161	.145	.113
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.188^c	.200^{c,d}	.200^{c,d}

According to the aforementioned normality test, there were twenty respondents from the control group in the pre-test; their mean score was 56.50 and their standard deviation was 3.62012. In the TRP 'experimental group' of 20 learners, 57.35 was the mean and the SD was 3.57292. Twenty students comprised the

DM experimental group, whereas the control groups mean 56.00with a standard deviation of 2.79096. Statistics for each group

demonstrated a normal distribution (sig. (2-tailed) = 0.188 (> 0.05) for the control group, ‘TRP experimental group’, and ‘DM experimental group’; sig. (2-tailed) = 0.200 (> 0.05).

After collecting data from each group, the authors used SPSS 25 for Windows 10 Pro's paired sample t-test to validate the contrasts between the groups. The disparities are laid forth in the table below:

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	CGPOTMARKS	58.7000	20	3.55557	.79505
	CGPRTMRKS	56.5000	20	3.62012	.80948
Pair 2	TRPPOTMARKS	68.7000	20	4.31765	.96546
	TRPPRETMARKS	57.3500	20	3.57292	.79893
Pair 3	DMPOTMARKS	61.7000	20	5.33213	1.19230
	DMPRETMARKS	56.0000	20	2.79096	.62408

Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	CGPOTMARKS - CGPRTMRKS	2.20	.69585	.15560	1.87433	2.52567	14.139	19	.000
Pair 2	TRPPOTMARKS - TRPPRETMARKS	11.35	2.64127	.59061	10.11385	12.58615	19.218	19	.000
Pair 3	DMPOTMARKS - DMPRETMARKS	5.70	3.07964	.68863	4.25868	7.14132	8.277	19	.000

2.20 marks is the mean differences of both test (pre- and post) scores of the ‘control group’ and Std. Deviation is 0.69585 while the TRP experimental group got 11.35 marks, with Std. Deviation 2.64127 and the DM experimental group got 5.70 marks with Std. Deviation 3.07964. The reader can notice in the ‘Paired Samples Test’. This research shows that TRP significantly increases students' ability to employ new vocabulary in their

everyday conversations in English. The use of DM was also associated with a little but statistically significant improvement, whereas the control group showed no such improvement.

Paired Samples Correlations

Paired Samples Correlations					
		N	Correlation	Sig.	
Pair 1	CGPOTMARKS & CGPRTMRKS	20	.981	.000	
Pair 2	TRPPOTMARKS & TRPPRETMARKS	20	.792	.000	
Pair 3	DMPOTMARKS & DMPRETMARKS	20	.898	.000	

In Paired Samples Correlations, we noticed The 2 tail significant values for each pair is less than 0.05, we can conclude that TRP has resulted in a statistically significant increase in both vocabulary and fluency and little bit by DM.

Pre – Test Questionnaire Frequency Test in SPSS

After analysing the obtained score data, the researcher plans to do an SPSS frequency analysis on the responses to the questionnaire. In the pre-test, we asked the participant the questions listed below. In the table below, you'll see how the respondents answered the survey

Do you think your current teaching method is more theoretical and less practical?

Do you think your current teaching technique doesn't give an English-speaking environment and vocabulary growth to help you learn?

Do you believe the lengthy translation process prevents people from speaking English fluently?

Is it hard to learn English without adequate vocabulary?

The results of this ‘pre-test’ frequency test observed that their current method of instruction does not provide them with the chance to use English in a practical context; moreover, they do not have access to an environment in which English is spoken. During talks, they find themselves at a lack of words. They are learning English via translation, which makes it difficult for them to speak English fluently owing to the prolonged nature of the translation process.

Descriptive Frequency Test

N	Valid	20	20	20	20	20
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	3.5500	3.5500	3.7500	3.7000	3.5500
	Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
	Mode	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

The descriptive frequency test that is now being used demonstrates that the present mode of instruction is not as effective vocabulary teaching. According to the results of the questionnaire that were presented earlier, the vast majority of respondents selected the fourth available option, which was labeled "agree." This indicates that the respondents believe that the present method of instruction is not adequate to assist them enrich their stock of words and speaking skills. The fact that the mean responses to the aforementioned question were 3.55, 3.55, and 3.75, 370, 355 respectively, which are all very close to the number 4, demonstrates that the majority of respondents concur that they are not happy with their current teaching method, which needs to be changed as soon as possible.

Post – Test TPR Questionnaire Frequency Test in SPSS

Descriptive Frequency Test

N	Valid	20	20	20	20	20
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	3.7000	4.2500	4.1000	3.5500	3.9000
	Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
	Mode	4.00	4.00^a	4.00	4.00	4.00

After finishing the study described above and analysing the data, the researcher came to the conclusion that after conducting the ‘post - test’ of the "control group" on TRP method that there is a noticeable impact on enhancing students' vocabulary and English communication skills. This conclusion was reached after the author organised the ‘post test’ on TRP method. The experimental group consisted of twenty different pupils, and the overwhelming majority of them opted with choice number 4 ('Agree'). The responses included averages of 3.70, 4,25 4,10 3.55, and 3.90, which are all extremely close to 4, showing that the maximum of participants think that TRP assists in improving vocabulary and English sp vocabulary and English communication skills speaking ability.

Post – Test DM Questionnaire Frequency Test in SPSS

Descriptive Frequency Test

N	Valid	20	20	20	20	20
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	4.0500	3.9000	3.7500	4.2000	3.5500
	Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
	Mode	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

According to this research analysis, it has been noticed that the DM Method is superior to the current educational approach in enhancing students' vocabulary and proficiency test in English speaking ability. Twenty members of the DM "experimental group" consistently choose option 4 when given the choice ("Agree"). In contrast to the current DM 'experimental group' teaching method, the vast majority of respondents favour the DM Method. The median frequency response was 4, with the mean for each question coming in at 4.05, 3.90, 3.75, 4.20, and 3.55, all close to 4.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distributions of CGPRTMARKS, CGPOTMARKS, EGPRTMARKS, EGPOTTPRMRK, EGPRTDMMARK and EGPOTDMMARK are the same.	Related-Samples Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

- The expected null hypothesis was there is no significant impact of TRP and DM in occupying new vocabulary that helps the learner to adopt fluent English speaking ability much better than earlier methods of teaching.
- The expected alternative was that there is a significant effect of TRP and DM in occupying new vocabulary that helps the learner to adopt fluent English speaking ability much better than earlier methods of teaching. Thus the hypothesis test summary is rejecting null hypothesis and accepting alternative hypothesis.

The Research Results and Findings.

This study compared TRP with DM for teaching new vocabulary. The authors conducted pre-tests for the first time to determine students' abilities before providing any new teaching method. The average 'pre-test' marks for the 'TRP experimental group', 'DM experimental group and 'control groups' were 57.35 and 65.30, and 56.50 respectively. 'Pre-test' scores indicated that all three groups had similar skill levels. The average marks of the 'experimental group' improved after receiving the new teaching method compared to the initial marks score of all pre-test groups. 'TRP experimental group' 'post-test' score was 68.70, 'DM experimental group' 'post-test' marks was 61.70, and the 'control group' 'post-test' marks was 58.70.

During the trial, the control group only improved by 2.20 points which is no significant change but, the TRP experimental group improved by 11.35 points which are huge significant different from its pre-test, and the DM experimental group improved by 5.70 points from the pre-test. As a result, TRP outperformed 'Direct Method' in English vocabulary teaching to students in secondary and upper secondary schools. From the pre-test results, it was possible to determine that the average post-test marks of the 'experimental group' was higher than that of the 'control group'. In the pre-test, the mean score of the control group was 58.70, 'DM experimental group' was 65 and 'TRP experimental group' was 57.35, while in the 'post-test', the mean score had increased dramatically to 68.70 after being taught via TPR. It means that the TRP approach to English vocabulary teaching to secondary school students was more successful than the Direct Method. Students in both experimental groups showed significant gains in English vocabulary, but the control group could increase 2.20 points only, it suggests that the current approach is inadequate. In contrast, students in 'the experimental group' who taught with TPR were too engaged, positive, and outgoing than those in the control group. When the approach to instruction matched the needs of the pupils, they paid greater attention. With the right approach, they may be more motivated to study English. Students were able to overcome their fear of learning a new language and better grasp its meaning via the use of TPR, which included them physically acting out the language's meaning.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

The present study's findings suggest that the proposed TRP led to a significant increase in pupils' vocabulary knowledge in secondary school next to the DM approach. They were able to take pleasure in the process of learning and were thus inspired to expand their English vocabulary. The children could not reply to the teacher's commands before receiving the proposed approach. Now they can respond, provide comments, and comprehend the language after being taught to utilise TRP and 'Direct Method'. The Direct Method might boost vocabulary performance among pupils. Furthermore, it has been shown that although students had difficulty understanding concepts when taught directly, this problem disappeared after being exposed to TPR. This demonstrates that TRP is preferable to DM in secondary schools when English is taught as a non-native language.

Based on these research findings, we suggest the following recommendations for readers, teachers and others researchers: TRP is a powerful method for increasing English vocabulary in secondary school pupils. Their teachers should inspire children and help them develop their imaginations. Therefore, students should study English without fear and should "enjoy," "participate," and "practise" English regularly on daily basis, whether in writing or speaking. An additional study testing the efficacy of the TRP and 'Direct Method' in enhancing public speaking skills is welcome, as is an exploration of the other new aspects by other researchers.

References

1. Kothari, C. R. (n.d.). *Methods and Techniques. (2nd Revised Ed.)*. New Delhi.
2. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2017). *Approaches and methods in language teaching create eBook* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
3. Asher, J. J. (2009). *Learning Another Language Thought Action: Total Physical Response. Sky Oask Production*.
4. Brown, H. D. (2000). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching (4thed)*. Longman.
5. *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach Language Pedagogy(2nded)*. (2001). Longman.
6. Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2017). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). London, England: Routledge.
7. Curtain, H., & Dahlberg, C. A. (2010). *Language and Children: Making the Match, New Language for Young Learners, Grade K-8,4/E*. Allyn& Bacon.
8. Arikunto, S. (2006). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta*.
9. Brown, H. Douglas. (2015). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy etext* (4th ed.). Philadelphia, PA: Pearson Education.
10. Cameron, L. (2011). *Cambridge language teaching library: Teaching languages to young learners*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
11. El-Koumy, A. S. A. (2004). *Teaching and Learning English as A Foreign Language: A Comprehensive Approach. USA: Educational Resources Information Center. ERIC*.
12. Fraenkel, J., Wallen, N., & Hyun, H. (2022). *How to design and evaluate research in education ISE* (11th ed.). Columbus, OH: McGraw-Hill Education.
13. Ghani, G. (2014). The Effectiveness of Total Physical Response (TPR) Approach in Helping Slow Young Learners with Low Achievement Acquire English as A Second Language. *International Journal of Research in Social Science*, 4(6).
14. (N.d.-a). doi:323128.
15. Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Methods and Techniques. (2nd Revised Ed.)*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
16. (N.d.-b). doi:tadris.v4i2.4071.
17. Naeini, N., & Nekoui, M. (2016). Relationship between Gender and Vocabulary Teaching Methodology among Iranian EFL Children: A Comparison of TPR and Direct Method. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 7, 60–74.
18. Sariyati, I. (2013). The Effectiveness of TPR (Total Physical Response) Method in English Vocabulary Mastery of Elementary School Children. *PAROLE: Journal of Linguistics and Education*, 3, 50–64.
19. (N.d.-c). doi:assehr.k.200225.110.
20. Vega, A., & Rogel, E. Q. (n.d.). *Total Physical Response Method To Enhance Vocabulary For 4 Th Graders At Escuela De Educación Basica Ing*.
21. (N.d.-d). doi:eternal.v4i1.1946.
22. Fitria, R., & Rahila, C. D. I. (2020). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' VOCABULARY MASTERY. *INOVISH JOURNAL*, 5, 156–171.
23. Ilmi, P., Amara, K., & Dzurotul. (2022). STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY AT BAN NONSAWAN SCHOOL, THAILAND. *Journal of Languages and Language Teaching*, 10, 266–275.